

ROLE OF WOMEN IN SOCIETY, SOCIAL LEVEL

Axrarova Sevara Axmedovna

Tashkent State Technical University

Department of philosophy and national idea

Doctor of philosophy, temporary doer professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8378980>

Annotation: today, not only the role of Uzbek women in the upbringing of families and children is incomparable, but also the contribution they contribute to the development of our country. Today, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to ensure the rights, legitimate interests of women, to realize their abilities and capabilities, in a word, to make our sisters equal, active and creative members of society.

Keywords: Woman, Society, Social career, upbringing, nationality, family, child, potential, etiquette, Law, future

It is characteristic of the Uzbek people to glorify a woman, to pay tribute to her as a family flower, educator of the future generation, follower of the nation. the scope of efforts in such priority areas as social activation of women, promotion of rights and interests, strengthening their health, realization of their intellectual potential, involvement in entrepreneurship is growing, ultimately increasing their prestige both in the family and in the life of the state and society. After all, the equality of women with men, the state protection of family, motherhood and childhood are also enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today, not only the role of Uzbek women in the upbringing of families and children is incomparable, but also the contribution they contribute to the development of our country. Today, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to ensure the rights, legitimate interests of women, to realize their abilities and capabilities, in a word, to make our sisters equal, active and creative members of society. It will not be a mistake to say that the emphasis on strengthening the social protection of women, including ensuring employment, strengthening health, protecting motherhood and childhood, improving their standard of living, has risen to a high level.

As women's committees are aware of women's issues, it is a challenge to take nearly practical measures to address them. To carry out such work, it is necessary to know a woman full-fledged, understand. To realize this more fully, it is necessary to look at the history of a woman. In ancient times, a woman did not touch the production of food, her task was to wait for her husband in a cave, cook a mammoth with a man, equip a house, raise children. At that time, people lived in groups, and a woman could not choose a man for herself. The man began to create a family and chose a healthy woman for himself. In the future, women began to participate in hunting, the task of which was to trap the animal with stones. This was an early manifestation of the woman's gradual equality with men. In antiquity, the consciousness of people developed further, in many countries the worship of women, their appreciation and listening occurred. In ancient Greece, the role of women in family and society was a pure state assignment. The woman's task was to tell her husband what to do and how to do it correctly,

to guide him. There were no love marriages at the time, all relationships and families were built in accordance with political interests. Having children was also a state-mandated task. If a woman cannot conceive, it means that a man has the right to bring another home. Of course, the man did not marry her, his wife was considered one, but the relationship was revealed in front of everyone. If such a typical wife gave birth to children, then they became a full-fledged heir.

During the time of the former Union, it was the woman who was responsible for the safety of the family, the upbringing of children and their future life. No matter what happened in the family, the woman was to blame. Because the psychology of their citizens was built in such a way that a woman was responsible for the mistakes of all men. It was considered a shame that a woman could not engage in household activities, please her husband. It was a shame for him to have a divorce or a child without marriage. Everything that a husband and a child sought was considered a woman's dignity, then she became an exemplary citizen, a good housewife. Children did not dare to obey their mother. The woman was engaged in family life, kept accounting, went to work like a man. At that time, there were different roles in the male and female family. The Social Sciences of this period indicate that a man worked for the benefit of the motherland, and a woman for the well-being of the family. The achievements of a man were directly related to what a woman strives for in family life.

Women have always been distinguished by flexible intelligence and cunning. Many rulers sought the throne because of these qualities. Some women were able to so avert their husbands that the story was built according to their script. An example of this is the Ukrainian girl Roxolana. She was the beloved wife of the Eastern ruler because of her intelligence and beauty, and pushed her predecessor into the background. He became not only a wife, but also a friend, which is rare in Eastern families. She was his closest advisor, and her husband did everything that Roxolana, a former Tatar prisoner and concubine, advised him. In its history, there were many powerful and powerful female rulers like her.

Since the social role of women in society is now radically changed, naturally, the position of the fair sex in the current reality is also changing. Today, psychologists have divided women into the following categories of women:

- * leaders;
- * careerists;
- Housewives;
- * people of independent professions.

Leading women in many ways have similar character traits to men: they believe in their own strength according to the goal and achieve everything on their own without hoping for anyone's help. The leadership trait is not all female. A woman with leadership skills performs not only the role of leadership, but also other roles related to her without difficulty.

Self-awareness is the main goal of careerist women who always prioritize work and career achievements. Only after such results can they think about starting a family and planning children. The position of a woman who chose the role of a housewife in modern society, as a rule, is not considered from the best side today. Of course, in some cases, a woman is very pleased to act only as a keeper of the hearth and a faithful friend of her husband. But often this choice is due to such characteristics as selfishness, possessiveness, jealousy, etc. inherent in the character of the spouse. In the upbringing of a harmonious generation, first of all, raising the atmosphere of the family, family spirituality, further

strengthening respect and attention to women is one of the requirements of today. Because the young spiritually harmonious generation, which is our future, comes of age in this family environment, thanks to the upbringing in this family. In the family, for example: the inability to see a neighbor, fisqu fasod, the environment of igvo prevail, leaving, without a doubt, severe complications that cannot be corrected in the child's memory. Generally speaking, it is necessary for people who have the greatest honor as every parent living in Uzbekistan to realize that a child grows up either kind and compassionate or selfish and tolerant due to the family environment and upbringing. It is painful for them to first improve their family environment, to consider it sacred, to feel that their Super responsibility in raising a child is strong, as well as that they are contributing to the development and rise of an independent Uzbekistan through a huge responsible task. That is to say, there is no doubt that any child raised in a healthy family environment will have a harmonious generation.

As for independent professions, artists, journalists and poets are often simply passionate about their work. They should not be confused with careerists, because career growth is not important to them, but the opportunity to do what they love. For them, this often comes first, while the family disappears in the background. There are some qualities that are useful for a woman to lead a comfortable and cheerful family life. These are:

The ability to create harmony at home

Attention to children

Respect for a man

It is necessary to start changing

To look beautiful

The past must be left behind

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that a woman should prioritize her unique abilities and skills. Because a woman has a strong strength. Much stronger than men. If a woman wants something, she will achieve her desire in any way. The role of a woman is not to compete with men, but to achieve more, better, real things in synergy.

References:

- 1.Здравомыслова, О. Статус и карьера женщины в современных условиях. – М., 2000.
- 2.Зуйкова, Е.М., Ерусланова, Р.И. Феминология: Учебное пособие. – М.: Издательско-книготорговый центр «Маркетинг», 2001.
- 3.Пронин, А.А. Положение женщин в современной России: общая характеристика. – М., 2000.
- 4.Черняк, Е.М. Социология семьи: перспективы развития института. – М., 2000.
- 5.Мороз В.А., Аверкина Т.О. Социальные роли современной женщины в представлении студентов// Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований. – 2016. – № 11-4. – С. 726-731;